

Report Details

Report Location C:\Users\Administrator\Desktop\MARIANMARIAN_PBG.pdf
 Report Creator Administrator
 Report Date Friday, May 31, 2024 8:14 AM

Sample Details

Sample Name PBG
 Sample Description PBG By Administrator Date Friday, May 31 2024
 Analyst Administrator
 Creation Date 5/31/2024 8:10:28 AM
 X-Axis Units cm-1
 Y-Axis Units %T

Instrument Details

Instrument Model Spectrum Two
 Instrument Serial Number 99999
 Software Revision NIOS2 Main 00.02.0104 21-February-2018 16:08:00
 Number of Scans 24
 Resolution 4

Spectrum Graph

Name	Description
PBG	PBG By Administrator Date Friday, May 31 2024